

Antiferromagnetic Interaction in Binuclear Copper(II) Complexes Involving Tetradentate Schiff Bases

P. K. BHATTACHARYA

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002

THE area of homodinuclear complexes has invited the attention of many chemists because of their interesting electronic spectral and magnetic properties and their application as homogeneous catalysts in molecular activation processes and as models for the metalloenzymes and the developments have been comprehensively reviewed¹⁻³. Sinn and Harris have reported the binuclear and trinuclear complexes of the type $[\text{Cu}(\text{TSB})_2 \text{Cu Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{TSB})_2 \text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$, where TSB is various tetradentate Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and 2-OH-acetophenone. The mononuclear complex of the tetradentate Schiff base has an additional lone pair of electrons over the two phenolate O^- . It can react with the chlorides of the same metal when a homobinuclear complex results. However, if the TSB complex of a metal ion is made to react with the chloride of another metal ion, a heterobinuclear complex results.

Synthesis of binuclear Cu(II) complexes of the type II⁴ and III^{5,6} have also been reported, where the phenolate O^- of bi- or tri-dentate Schiff base acts as bridge between the two Cu(II) centres.

Binuclear complexes of Cu(II) was also obtained by the treatment of cupric isobutyrate with the Schiff bases derived from the reaction of *o*-aminophenol or alkanolamine with 3-formyl-5-methylsalicylaldehyde (IV)⁷. This differs from the earlier complexes in the fact that both the metal ions are bound to the same ligand. The ligand provides two coordination sites for the metal ions to be bound.

Formation of closed double compartment Cu(II) binuclear complexes, bridged through O^- , have also been reported in the cases of macrocyclic Schiff base ligands obtained by condensing 2-OH isophthalaldehyde with diamines (V)^{8,9}.

$\text{R} = \text{H or CH}_3$
 $n = 2, 3, 4, \text{ or } 6$
 $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^- \text{ or } \text{NO}_3^-$
 $\text{M} = \text{Cu(II) or Ni(II)}$

I

$\text{R} = \text{OMe}$

IV

$\text{R} = \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ or C_6H_5
 $\text{R}' = \text{H or } 5\text{-Cl}$
 $\text{X} = \text{Cl or Br}$
 $\text{M} = \text{Cu(II)}$

II

$\text{R} = (\text{CH}_2)_2\text{- or } -(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{-}$
 $\text{M} = \text{Cu(II), Ni(II),}$
 Co(II), Fe(II)
 or Mn(II)

V

In these binuclear Cu(II) complexes it has been observed that the magnetic moments are subnormal and decrease with decreasing temperature. This has been explained to be due to antiferromagnetic interaction between the two Cu(II) centres. In dimeric Cu(II) acetate, it was pointed out by Martin and Figgis¹⁰ and later by Kettle¹¹ that the distance between the two Cu(II) centres is less and hence a weak metal interaction is possible. However, in the complexes of the present type, Cu(II)-Cu(II) the distance is large and hence it seems unlikely that the direct exchange due to overlap of copper d orbitals is significant. The possible exchange pathway is super exchange involving copper $d_{x^2-y^2}$ and oxygen p_x orbitals. This interaction gives rise to a diamagnetic ground state and an excited paramagnetic triplet state. The separation between the two states is equal to $2J$ value, where J is the value of spin exchange interaction. It is given by the following equation :

$$J = \int (\Psi_{a(1)} \Psi_{b(2)}) / \text{Hex} / \Psi_{b(1)} \Psi_{a(2)} \delta T_1 \delta T_2$$

where the hamiltonian operator,

$$\text{Hex} = \frac{e^2}{r_{12}} + \frac{2a^*2b^*e^2}{R} - \frac{2b^*e^2}{r_{1b}} - \frac{2a^*e^2}{r_{2a}}$$

If $2J \geq KT$, all the molecules are in the singlet ground state and the binuclear complex is diamagnetic. When $2J = KT$, the magnetic susceptibility depends on the Boltzman population of the states. The temperature dependance of the susceptibility (χ_m) is given by the equation suggested by Bleany and Bowers.

The magnitude of J can be determined from a fit of the experimental data of χ_m and T to the above equation or may be estimated from T_{max} (the temperature at which χ_m is maximum) in the plot of T against magnetic susceptibility.

For the exchange interaction to occur between the two Cu(II), it is necessary that the binuclear complex should have a planar structure. Any distortion from planarity would reduce the overlap of Cu(II) $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals with oxygen p_x orbital, and the exchange interaction is weakened. A convenient measure of the degree of distortion from planarity is the angle T between the plane of the Cu_2O bridge and that of the remaining ligands. For a complete planar structure it will be zero and will increase with tetrahedral distortion at the two Cu(II) centres. On this basis, super exchange in the complexes of the type II should be more than that in I⁶. It is actually observed that type II complexes exhibit much larger singlet-triplet separation (300 cm^{-1} or more) and the magnetic property do not differ significantly from complex to complex. In complexes of type I, the J value is less and the magnetic property differs significantly from compound to compound. These properties can be explained by considering that complexes II have *trans* structure. The *trans* structure helps the complex to attain more of planar structure and hence the exchange interaction is more. If R groups on N are bulkier, there is steric distortion towards tetrahedral and magnetic

moment goes up. The band position in the ligand field spectra of these complexes also show that the Cu(II) in these binuclear complexes is in a square planar field. With substitution of bulky R groups, there is tetrahedral distortion with λ_{max} moving to higher wavelength region. Thus, there is a linear relationship between the d-d band wavelength and the magnetic moments of the complexes. The same relationship holds good in type III complexes also^{6,12}.

In the complexes of type I, the two phenolate O^- of the TSB are on the same side. In $[\text{Cu}(\text{TSB})]$ itself, the structure of the ligand around Cu(II) is distorted from planarity. In the binuclear complexes, on coordination with CuCl_2 , the

part has a pseudo tetrahedral structure. This induces more planarity on the $[\text{Cu}(\text{TSB})]$ part. It was observed by Sinn⁴ that if one of the metal ions is in a planar environment, the adjacent metal ion will be distorted away from planarity, and if one of them is in a tetrahedral environment, the adjacent metal will be distorted away from tetrahedral geometry. As distortion from planarity increases, there is a lowering in the antiferromagnetic interaction, resulting in increase in the magnetic moment. But with tetrahedral distortion there is a lowering in the ligand field with consequent increase in λ_{max} . Thus, linear relationship between magnetic moment and λ_{max} value holds good in these complexes also.

In case of type I $[\text{Cu}(\text{TSB})\text{CuCl}_2]$ complexes, it was observed¹ that there is a steady increase in the magnetic moment and λ_{max} values as we move to the TSB with increasing length of the carbon chain joining the N atoms. This is because there is an increased distortion from planar to pseudo tetrahedral form in the geometry of the $[\text{Cu}(\text{TSB})]$ with increasing chain length. Increasing distortion from planar towards tetrahedral geometry causes an increase in the magnetic moment and a shift to lower energy of the ligand band.

There is no systematic relation observed between the magnetic moments and Cu-O-Cu' angle in type II and III complexes. This is probably because the angle does not vary enough to show a significant effect. Since the super exchange takes place between the Cu(II) centres and O^- , the environment around them have the maximum effect on the J value¹².

In these complexes, (I, II and III), substitution over the phenyl ring of the Schiff base can affect the J value to the extent they alter the Cu-O-Cu bridge via alteration of molecular packing. Nature of R over $-\text{C}=\text{N}$ part also does not affect the properties significantly. TSB derived from 2-OH-acetophenone or 2-OH-benzophenone forms binuclear Cu(II) complexes with magnetic moment not significantly different from TSB derived from salicylaldehyde¹².

In case of type I binuclear complexes of TSB of $\text{N,N}'$ -ethylene bis-salicylaldehyde (ES) and $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$,

It was observed that there is a possibility of linkage of the halogen with the Cu(II) of the adjacent molecule making it five coordinated and weakening one of the Cu-O bonds. This results in a weakening of the antiferromagnetic interaction and lowering of J value.

Sinn and coworkers¹⁴ studied the pressure dependence of magnetic susceptibility in the range 1–3000 atm. In cases of type II complexes there is little effect on magnetism with X=Cl or Br. This is because they have very similar structure, and the electronic effect, which might have been affected, is not evident.

However, when X=NO₃⁻¹⁵, the second oxygen of the already coordinated NO₃⁻ is in close proximity to the Cu(II) of another binuclear complex. Thus, there is formation of a weaker Cu-O bond due to intermolecular interaction and the geometry at each Cu(II) is square pyramidal. This apical bond reduces the super-exchange overlap, reducing J value. The way it is brought about is not clear because the Cu-O-Cu bridge angle is not affected significantly.

The spectral characteristics of the binuclear complexes are also interesting. In case of type III complexes of bidentate Schiff bases⁴, only one band is observed, though shifted from the band position of the mononuclear complex. This shows that the two Cu(II) atoms have equivalent ligand field in type II complex. The position of the band also shows that the structure of the two centres is planar and this is in keeping with the *trans* structure. The same is true in case of type III complexes also. However, in type I complexes involving TSB, there are two non-equivalent Cu(II) centres and hence two bands are observed. In the CuCl₂ part bonded to the two O⁻ of the Cu(TSB), Cu(II) is in a tetrahedral environment and hence band is observed in the region 8000–12000 cm⁻¹ as expected in tetrahedral Cu(II) complexes. The original band of mononuclear TSB complex, occurring at ~17000 cm⁻¹, shows a shift on coordination with CuCl₂. The band shifts to the higher energy region indicating that the complex ligand becomes more planar when it coordinates with CuCl₂. This energy shift confirms that there is formation of binuclear complex.

Their spectral studies also support the formation of the binuclear complex⁴. There is an increase in the constraint on the vibration of the Schiff base part of [Cu(TSB)] on its coordination with CuX₂. This results in a shift of the ir bands of [Cu(TSB)] part in the region 1620, 1480, 1140, 1040 and 760 cm⁻¹ to higher energy by about 5–10 cm⁻¹ in the binuclear complex. The band near 1530 cm⁻¹ is due to phenolic C-O stretching. This is most affected by the coordination of the [Cu(TSB)] to CuX₂ and shows a shift of about 15 to 20 cm⁻¹.

It is thus observed that the nature of X on the second copper centre may affect the properties of the [Cu(TSB)CuX₂] complexes. We have carried out¹⁶ the study of binuclear Cu(II) complexes

formed by the coordination of tetradentate Schiff base complex with a metal ion already bound to another bidentate ligand. Complexes of the type [Cu(TSB)Cu(A-A)](ClO₄)₂ have been prepared where TSB=tetradentate Schiff bases like N-N'-ethylene (or propylene) *bis*salicylaldehyde, N-N'-ethylene (or propylene) *bis*-2-OH-aceto-phenonimine, A-A=tertiary diamines like 2,2'-dipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline or 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole.

[Cu(TSB')CuX₂] and [Cu(TSB')Cu(A-A)](ClO₄)₂ binuclear complexes have also been synthesized¹⁷, where X=Cl or ClO₄, TSB' is an unsymmetrical tetradentate Schiff base like N-N'-ethylene (or propylene) salicylaldehyde-2-OH-aceto-phenonimine or N-N'-propylene salicylaldehyde-2-OH-1-naphthaldimine. [Cu(TSB)], where TSB=symmetrical or unsymmetrical tetradentate Schiff bases, were prepared by template synthesis followed by amine exchange^{18,19}. [Cu(TSB)Cu(A-A)](ClO₄)₂ complexes were synthesized by treating [Cu(TSB)] with [Cu(A-A)(ClO₄)₂]. The structure of the resulting binuclear complexes can be shown as below.

R = H
R' = H or CH₃
n = 2 or 3
X = Cl or ClO₄

VI

R = H or CH₃
R' = H or CH₃
n = 2 or 3
A-A = A¹, A² or A³

VII

The bridging phenolate O⁻ bond is very weak. Addition of water to the binuclear complexes breaks the bridge resulting in the separation of [Cu(TSB)] complex and [Cu(H₂O)₆]Cl₂, [Cu(H₂O)₆](ClO₄)₂, or [Cu(A-A)](ClO₄)₂.

The complexes are not sufficiently soluble in organic solvents and hence molar conductance could not be determined. IR spectra show that in type VI complexes, ClO₄⁻ are in the outer sphere. IR band corresponding to ν_{O-O}, shifts to higher energy region

in the binuclear complex confirming the coordination of the phenolate O⁻ with the second Cu(II) centre. The shift in ν_{O-O} in the [Cu(TSB)Cu(A-A)]²⁺ is of the same order as in [Cu(TSB)CuX₂].

The reflectance spectra of the complexes show two d-d bands corresponding to the two non-equivalent Cu(II) centres. In type VI complexes, >CuX₂ centre shows a band at 8500-10000 cm⁻¹ similar to that observed by Sinn and coworkers¹.

However, >Cu(A-A) part in type VII complexes shows a band at higher energy 12500 cm⁻¹. This is because A-A creates a stronger field than the two chlorides. The band, due to [Cu(TSB)] part in both types of binuclear complexes, show a shift from the free [Cu(TSB)] value. This is because of the change in the planarity of [Cu(TSB)] on coordination with CuX₂ or [Cu(A-A)]²⁺, as explained in earlier studies². Further, coordination with CuCl₂ or [Cu(A-A)]²⁺ also lowers the strength of Cu(II)-O bond in the [Cu(TSB)] part. There is no significant difference in the lowering of [Cu(TSB)] band position in [Cu(TSB)CuCl₂] or [Cu(TSB)Cu(A-A)]²⁺.

Magnetic moments of the complexes at room temperature were found to be lower than that expected for one unpaired electron on each Cu(II) ion. This indicates antiferromagnetic spin-exchange interaction. In these complexes also Cu-Cu distance is too big for direct interaction between the metal ion. The super exchange must be taking place through σ interaction of Cu(II) d_{xy} orbitals with the s and p orbitals of the bridging diamagnetic O⁻ of the Schiff base. Spin exchange integral J could not be calculated in the absence of variable temperature magnetic data and hence its value in type VI and type VII complexes could not be compared. However, the lowering in the magnetic moment values in the two cases do not differ significantly.

One interesting point of difference is that in case of type VI complexes, the lowering in the magnetic moment is less in complexes with TSB having a long -(CH₂)_n- chain, as reported earlier¹. But in the type VII complexes there is an increase in the lowering of magnetic moment in case of TSB with -(CH₂)₃- than in case of TSB with -(CH₂)₂-. The explanation for this observation has to await X-ray crystal study of the complexes showing the extent of distortion in planarity at the two Cu(II) centres.

The possibility of super exchange interaction through the metal d π orbital and the π orbitals of the O⁻ has been ruled out by the uv spectra of [Cu(TSB)], [Cu(A-A)]²⁺ and the binuclear complex [Cu(TSB)Cu(A-A)]²⁺. It is observed that the uv bands in the binuclear complexes have almost one to one correspondence with the bands of [Cu(TSB)] and [Cu(A-A)]²⁺. Any interaction between the π orbitals of the TSB and bipyridyl through the metal ion should have changed the position of the near uv bands of the binuclear complex.

In order to prove this point, monomeric Cu(II) complexes of saturated tetradentate bases, obtained

by the reaction of NaBH₄ on the Schiff base, were prepared. The extent of π delocalization in these complexes is lower than in the original [Cu(TSB)]. The mononuclear complex was treated with CuX₂ and [Cu(A-A)(ClO₄)₂] to prepare complexes of the type [Cu(MB)CuX₂] and [Cu(MB)Cu(A-A)](ClO₄)₂²⁰. The structures are as follows.

R = H or CH₃
X = Cl or ClO₄
n = 2 or 3

VIII

R = H or CH₃
A-A = A¹, A² or A³
n = 2 or 3

IX

These complexes also show two d-d bands in the ligand field spectra corresponding to the two Cu(II) centres. There is also a lowering in the magnetic moment showing super exchange interaction. The extent of lowering in the magnetic moment is of the same order as in case of type VI and type VII complexes. This shows that restricting the π delocalization in the tetradentate ligand part does not affect the extent of super exchange. It can, therefore, be said that the π orbitals have no significant role to play in the super exchange interaction.

References

1. S. J. GRUBER, C. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, 30, 1805.
2. M. KATO, K. IMAI, Y. MUTO, T. TOKII and H. B. JONASSEN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, 35, 109.
3. E. SINN and C. M. HARRIS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, 4, 391.
4. C. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, 30, 2723.
5. J. A. DAVIS and E. SINN, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1976, 165.
6. M. KATO, Y. MUTO, H. B. JONASSEN, K. IMAI, K. KATSUKI and S. IKEGAMI, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1969, 42, 2555.
7. R. ROBSON, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.*, 1970, 6, 125.
8. R. R. GAGNE, C. A. KOVAL, T. J. SMITH and M. C. CIMOLINO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 101, 4571.
9. S. L. LAMBERT and D. N. HENDRICKSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, 18, 2683.

BHATTACHARYA : ANTIFERROMAGNETIC INTERACTION IN BINUCLEAR COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

10. B. N. FIGGIS and R. L. MARTIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 3837.
11. R. W. JOTHAM and S. F. A. KETTLE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A), 1969, 2816, 2821.
12. E. SINN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 15, 358.
13. P. GLUVCHINSKY, G. M. MOCKLER, P. C. HEALY and E. SINN, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1974, 11, 1156.
14. E. SINN and W. T. ROBINSON, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Comm.*, 1972, 359.
15. E. SINN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 15, 366.
16. K. V. PATEL and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1982, 359.
17. K. V. PATEL and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, (in press)
18. B. T. THAKER and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, 37, 615.
19. B. T. THAKER and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1976, 49, 2845.
20. K. V. PATEL and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.* (communicated).